

ECONOMY

Ho Chi Minh City: Choosing the right key point to break through

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(TTCO) - A successful strategy lies in choosing the right location. For Ho Chi Minh City, it is “connecting infrastructure and interconnected data”. Once this step is solved, the remaining tasks will become simple.

Identify key moments

In my childhood memories, there is a story that seems very small but leaves a big lesson about strategy. My family is poor, with many siblings, my parents work hard every day on the newly cleared barren land. Although they did not study much, my parents clearly understood that only education could help their children escape poverty.

Therefore, despite the lack of money, they were determined to send all eight children to school. At one point, faced with the burden of making a living, my father considered letting my second sister drop out of school to work to help support the family. But my mother firmly maintained her opinion: “My second child’s education is the most important thing.”

She explained that my second sister was the eldest child, and if she studied well, she would set an example for her younger siblings; when she graduated, she would have a stable job to help support her younger siblings through school; and her success would open a way out of poverty for the whole family. Indeed, that decision changed fate: from the example and support of my second sister, all seven younger siblings were able to get an education, and my parents' aspiration to "escape poverty" became a reality.

The story leaves a truth: among all the things to do, you must identify the key point. Once the key point is solved, it will create a ripple effect, making other problems easier. For Ho Chi Minh City today, after expanding from three dynamic industrial provinces, that lesson still holds true.

After the merger, Ho Chi Minh City will have hundreds of tasks to implement in the next 5 years: urban development, industry, logistics, financial services, improving social security, environmental protection, green transformation, digital transformation... But if resources are spread out and the right key points to connect the tasks are not chosen,

the city will easily fall into a state of dispersion and lack of focus, leading to low efficiency.

So what is the “key point” to focus on? With the expansion of Ho Chi Minh City, that breakthrough point is the “connecting infrastructure and interconnected data”.

Breakthrough from infrastructure and data

When connectivity infrastructure is prioritized, the flow of goods, labor and services will operate smoothly, logistics costs will be reduced, and regional industry and trade will be strongly activated. Connective infrastructure is the path that opens up for the development of industry and services.

In the next 5 years, Ho Chi Minh City needs to focus on building a regional infrastructure network in three aspects: developing multimodal transport with synchronization between roads, railways, seaports, ICDs and airports to ensure smooth connections, reduce logistics costs and enhance business competitiveness; building energy infrastructure and green industrial parks to ensure stable supply of electricity, water, waste treatment and renewable energy development, meeting the requirements of sustainable growth; and re-planning industrial space in an integrated direction, arranging industrial parks and export processing zones into clusters and chains closely linked with urban areas and support services, thereby forming a modern production and trade ecosystem.

When data is interconnected, the administrative apparatus becomes more transparent and responsive, helping policies stay one step ahead and building trust among investors, businesses and citizens. A large urban - industrial region cannot continue to be governed by the old method.

In the next 5 years, Ho Chi Minh City needs to build a unified data warehouse, fully integrating information on residents, businesses, infrastructure, logistics, environment and labor; issue common data standards so that the government, businesses and people can connect and share, thereby reducing duplication and unnecessary procedures.

At the same time, promote the application of digital technology, artificial intelligence and big data analysis to support traffic forecasting, regulation, energy management as well as investment licensing in a quick and transparent manner.

The ripple effect from synchronized infrastructure and data

Once the infrastructure and data are synchronized, the entire development machine of Ho Chi Minh City will operate smoothly, leading to a series of other problems becoming simpler and more convenient.

First of all, attracting FDI and developing high-tech industry will become a clear advantage. International investors always carefully consider factors such as logistics costs, infrastructure quality and administrative convenience. When the multimodal transport system is completed, logistics is cheaper, along with a transparent and fast data-based management system, Ho Chi Minh City will become a leading attractive destination in the region.

Next, green transformation and innovation will have a foundation to break through. Stable energy infrastructure, smart grids, sustainable water and waste treatment combined with integrated data systems will create conditions for green technology projects, renewable energy, circular economy and innovative startups to thrive. This will be the driving force to move Ho Chi Minh City away from a growth model that relies heavily on labor and towards a model based on knowledge and technology.

At the same time, social management and urban security have also improved dramatically. When population, health, education, environment and infrastructure data are connected, the allocation of public services becomes more scientific, reducing waste and injustice. People have access to fair and quick services, while the government has more tools to adjust policies according to practical needs.

Finally, when these two pillars are consolidated, Ho Chi Minh City will affirm its role as the integrated center of the whole region. Not only solving its own development problems, the city will also become the nucleus that leads to the synchronous development of neighboring localities. A modern, dynamic and sustainable economic-urban region will be formed, increasing competitiveness not only at the national level but also at the regional scale.

Things to do in the next 5 years

To realize this orientation, Ho Chi Minh City needs to focus on four key groups of solutions. First of all, prioritize investment in infrastructure linked to beltway projects, inter-regional urban railways, transit seaports and green logistics centers to reduce transportation costs, shorten the time of goods circulation and improve competitiveness for the whole region.

Next is to build a regional data center that plays a core role in digital government, digital economy and digital society, ensuring the ability to connect and share information between sectors, localities and businesses.

At the same time, the city needs to reform its data-based governance system, apply a digital management system and integrate data into the entire licensing, monitoring and

evaluation process so that the administrative apparatus becomes transparent, efficient and responsive to fluctuations.

Finally, establish a specific regional coordination mechanism for Ho Chi Minh City and neighboring provinces to jointly operate infrastructure and data, ensuring consistency in planning, investment and management, thereby forming a combined strength for the entire economic region.

Developing a large urban-industrial area like the expanded Ho Chi Minh City is a huge task with countless challenges. However, success does not lie in doing everything at the same time, but in knowing how to choose the right key point to concentrate resources. For Ho Chi Minh City today, that key point is the connecting infrastructure and interconnected data in operations.

When infrastructure is smooth and data is synchronized, the remaining issues - from attracting FDI, green transformation, innovation, social reform to improving the quality of life - all become more convenient and effective. This is the strategic lever, the decision that shapes the future.

If determined to focus on this key point, Ho Chi Minh City can make a breakthrough to become the leading industrial - service - innovation center in the region, realizing the aspiration for strong and sustainable development in the period 2025-2030 and beyond.

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